

INFLUENCE OF SPECIMEN TWISTING ON FRACTURE SURFACE EVOLUTION IN THE SPLIT-SHEAR TORSION TEST

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ABSTRACT

The influence of specimen twisting during anti-plane shear (mode III) loading in composite split beam specimens is studied using the split-shear torsion test. Tests were conducted on specimens with different thicknesses and delamination lengths to produce different amounts of specimen twisting prior to fracture. It is shown that specimen twisting causes mode I stresses to develop that are proportional to the angle of twist, thereby producing mixed-mode I-III conditions along the delamination front. This causes near-tip transverse cracks to initiate, prior to delamination advance, at an orientation related to the mode mix, and therefore to the angle of twist. Unlike what occurs in homogeneous materials, it is observed that the laminate's fibers restrict the amount by which these transverse cracks can rotate during extension, and that transverse crack extension is accompanied by planar delamination advance. The overall fracture surface evolution is therefore strongly controlled by specimen and test geometry. The influence of these findings on the apparent delamination toughness as obtained from composite split beam tests, as well as on mode III delamination toughness testing in general, is discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Determination of the delamination toughness of laminated polymeric composites under anti-plane shear (mode III) loading has proven to be a complex issue. A variety of different test techniques have shown that the apparent mode III toughness, i.e., that which is obtained by any particular test and data reduction technique, depends upon both specimen and test geometry [1-5]. As such, no current test can be relied upon to produce a true material property. The reasons for this have been studied using both the split-shear torsion (SST) and edge crack torsion (ECT) tests [5-7]. These two tests utilize different specimen geometries and stacking sequences. However, both tests measure toughness considering growth from an insert that is pre-implanted between two plies with their fibers oriented in the intended growth direction. These studies have shown that, rather than the expected planar advance, fracture initially occurs via the initiation of transverse matrix cracks that are inclined at an angle to the delamination plane. This initiation process is similar to that which occurs in homogeneous and geologic materials subjected to anti-plane shear loading, where an array, or echelon, of cracks initially develops along the original crack front [8-13]. Cracks in the array are oriented at a 45° angle to the original crack plane, such that they are perpendicular to the direction of maximum tensile stress associated with the original mode III near-tip stress field. For homogeneous materials, macroscopic advance of the system occurs via extension of this array. This requires the initial crack front to fragment into a series of segments. The evolution of this system therefore produces a fracture surface that shows segmentation and macroscopic rotation towards the maximum tensile stress direction [11-16]. Similar behaviors occur under mixed mode I-III loadings of homogeneous materials [8,11,17-19], where it has recently been shown that any non-zero mode III component will induce this fragmentation

[20]. In contrast, in laminated composites, both the echelon array and the planar delamination have been shown to advance, with the former leading the latter [6,21]. The differences in fracture surface evolution between composite and homogeneous materials were shown to occur due to the composite's propensity for delamination growth along an interlaminar interface, the limitations on transverse crack size created by the relatively thin nature of the composite fracture specimens, and the energetic restrictions to fracture path twisting caused by the laminate's fibers [21].

Many of the preceding conclusions were obtained via the SST test, which utilizes a split beam type geometry. Studies using this geometry produced an apparent mode III delamination toughness, G_{IIIc} , which decreased with increasing delamination length [5,6]. Interestingly, it was observed during these experiments that the rotation, or angle of twist, of the uncracked portion of the specimen also increased with increasing delamination length. This motivated the present work, which aims to understand whether specimen twisting affects the toughness and/or the way in which the fracture surface evolves. Specifically, the goals of this study were to (1) understand why the apparent toughness obtained from SST tests decreases with increasing delamination length, (2) determine the relationship between specimen twist and apparent toughness, (3) determine the relationship between specimen twist and fracture surface evolution, and (4) relate the observed mechanisms to those that occur in homogenous materials under analogous conditions.

To achieve the above, SST specimens with different thicknesses and delamination lengths were manufactured and tested. After testing, specimens were sectioned transversely in the region where delamination growth occurred. Optical microscopy was used to observe the details of transverse cracking and delamination advance. These data were then combined with appropriate analyses to address the four specific goals above.

2 TESTING AND POST-TEST INSPECTIONS

2.1 Test Geometry and Specimen Preparation

Figure 1 presents a schematic representation of the SST test [5,6]. The specimen is unidirectional with all plies oriented in the x-direction. It contains a pre-implanted insert at its mid-plane that spans the specimen's width, B , and which creates a starter delamination of length a . As shown in the figure, load is introduced to the specimen through loading tabs and blocks. The upper load block (so-named as it attaches to the upper portion of the load frame) is fully constrained, and the lower load block is constrained such that only vertical translation may occur. Thus, both shear and torsional loadings are transmitted to the specimen. To maintain static equilibrium, the load blocks in the SST test produce a restoring torsional moment about the x-axis that is transmitted into each of the cracked regions. This produces an equal rate of twist in each cracked region, and therefore an angle of twist that increases linearly with distance from the load block. The restoring moments and torque produced by the applied load equilibrate to produce a load- and torsion-free uncracked region. Therefore, the angle of twist does not change within the uncracked region, but rather equals the value in each of the cracked regions at the delamination tip. Similar behavior occurs in the MSCB specimen [2,3]. In both tests, this produces an angle of twist of the uncracked region that, for a given applied load, increases with increasing delamination length.

Unidirectional IM7/8552 pre-preg tape was used to make all specimens. Twenty four- and 48-ply SST specimens with nominal thicknesses, $2h$, of 3.0 mm and 6.0 mm were fabricated for this study. Teflon inserts that were 13 μm thick and with lengths varying from 70 – 150 mm were implanted at the laminate's mid-plane during layup in order to produce specimens with delamination lengths, a , of 32 – 127 mm. All SST specimens were nominally sized to have widths, B , of 25.4 mm. These geometries were chosen to produce different amounts of specimen twisting prior to fracture.

As will be discussed subsequently, the data reduction method used for the SST test is sensitive to the values of the axial and shear moduli. Thus, in addition to obtaining SST specimens, two specimens were cut from the non-delaminated portion of each plate manufactured and used to determine the axial modulus (E_{11}) following ASTM Standard D3039 [22]. Relatively little variation was observed within or between plates. Testing to determine the shear modulus (G_{12}) followed ASTM Standard D5379 [23], and also produced relatively tight distributions. These experiments produced $E_{11} = 187.2$ GPa and $G_{12} = 7.33$ GPa.

2.2 Test Fixture

Photographs of the SST test fixture containing a specimen are presented in Figure 2. The tabbed specimen is sandwiched in-between two load block/grip assemblies. These are integral units, each of which contains two bolt holes and a backing plate that presses against the outer surface of the load tab. The upper assembly connects to the load cell and remains stationary during testing. The lower assembly is mounted to a platen that connects to the actuator and is displaced downwards during the test. As shown in the figure, this lower load block/grip assembly is bolted to the platen through slots. This allows it to slide during specimen installation and thereby to accommodate specimens of different thicknesses. The procedures to install specimens into the grips were developed to maximize reproducibility and are detailed in Ref. [5].

Figure 1: Schematic of SST test geometry and loading.

Figure 2: SST fixture (a) front view, (b) side view.

2.3 Specimen Rotation Measurement

Before testing, each SST specimen was masked using opaque tape as shown in Figure 3. One piece of tape is aligned with the delamination front and covers the entire width of the specimen. The other is oriented perpendicularly and is aligned to cover the majority of the specimen's width while leaving the outside edges unmasked. The intersections of the masking creates two corners that are used as reference points.

In order to visually capture changes in specimen rotation during testing, a digital camera is clamped to the test fixture platen of Figure 2. The camera lens is oriented orthogonally to the plane of the specimen, and is focused at the two reference points created by masking the specimen. The camera remains fixed in this location throughout the test. To begin the data acquisition process, an initial reference image of the unloaded specimen is taken. Images are then taken during testing approximately every 200 N, and again when the peak load is reached. Additional images are also captured during the specimen unloading, and a final image is taken once the specimen is fully unloaded.

The images captured during testing are evaluated using graphical analysis software. First, the distance between the masked corners is measured in pixels for the pre-test reference image. The distance between these two corners is then measured for each subsequent image. The difference between the reference distance and the distance measured for a given image is then used to determine the angle of twist of the specimen at each load.

2.4 Transverse Crack Measurement

In order to observe transverse cracks, SST specimens were destructively sectioned subsequent to testing using a diamond-tipped low-speed cut-off saw. Specimens were sectioned either just ahead of the initial delamination tip created by the Teflon insert, or at specific locations ahead of the insert. These section cuts were made transverse to the direction of planar delamination growth, such that the specimens' y-z planes were exposed. Cut sections were then potted in epoxy, polished, and viewed under a differential interference contrast (DIC) reflected light microscope. Photomicrographs of close-up sections were taken across the entire cross section, and later stitched together such that a full view of the transverse section was available for analysis. These sections were used to determine the

progression of the transverse matrix crack development and their interactions with the planar delamination as the entire system evolved. This evolution was subsequently correlated to an associated angle of twist.

3 ANALYSES

3.1 Energy Release Rate and Mode Mixity

In previous works, the energy release rate (ERR) distribution for SST specimens has been determined using 3D linear finite element (FE) analyses and the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [24,25]. This technique was used to partition the ERR, G , into its mode I, II, and III components in terms of the undeformed coordinate system, depicted using (y,z) in Figure 4. Figure 4b shows the cross-section at the delamination tip in its deformed state. This figure introduces a (y',z') system and the angle ϕ between the two coordinate systems. The (y',z') coordinate system defines the orientation of the delamination tip during deformation. The angle ϕ is a function of the applied load, P , and defines the angle of twist of the delamination tip and of the uncracked region.

Considering the geometry of Figure 4 and assuming solely planar delamination advance, previous studies [5,26] have shown that growth will initiate in the center of the specimen ($y=0$) where the ERR is a maximum. These references further showed that pure mode III conditions exist at this location. Further, the mode I component of ERR is zero everywhere, and the mode II component remains sufficiently small that predominantly mode III conditions exist over the specimen's entire width. Considering the VCCT calculations [25], this means that in the center of the specimen, only the multiplication associated with the y -components of the near-tip forces and displacements produce non-zero contributions to G . However, these analyses were performed with respect to the undeformed coordinate system. Transforming the y -components of force and displacement into the (y',z') system yields non-zero mode I and mode III components of ERR, G_I and G_{III} , respectively, as

$$G_I = G \sin^2 \phi ; G_{III} = G \cos^2 \phi \quad (1)$$

From Equation (1), the mode mixity, defined here as G_{III}/G_I , is given by

$$G_{III}/G_I = \cot^2 \phi \quad (2)$$

and is independent of the value of G . Since G_I , in terms of the undeformed coordinate system equals zero [5,26], these same equations may be applied to the linear FE results for G_{III} as a function of y . That is, the transformation given by Equation (1) applies to all elements along the delamination front. The small mode II components that arise are unaffected by this transformation.

Figure 3: Photograph of masked, tabbed SST specimen with $a = 32$ mm.

Figure 4: Schematic showing orientation of SST specimen cross-section (a) before and (b) after deformation.

3.2 Apparent Toughness

Following the same approach used in previous studies [5,26], in this work the apparent delamination toughness is calculated using the peak value of the local ERR, computed at the delamination onset load. The delamination onset load is defined as the peak load from the test, which was experimentally established as the load at which the onset of planar delamination growth occurred [26]. Fundamentally, this is achieved by using the peak load from the test along with a finite element model of the test and specimen. However, rather than perform a FE analysis of each individual specimen, an equation is used that has been calibrated to multiple FE results [5,6,27]. This equation, which yields the ERR in the center of the specimen, is given by

$$G = C_f(a, h) \frac{P^2}{B^2 h G_{12}} \left(0.66 + 1.15 \sqrt{\frac{G_{12}}{E_{11}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Here, P is the applied anti-plane shear load, B is the specimen width, h is the specimen half thickness, E_{11} is the modulus in the fiber direction, and G_{12} is the in-plane shear modulus. $C_f(a, h)$ is a correction factor that depends on thickness and delamination length. It is extracted from a FE analysis of a single specimen for each geometry tested. Values for $C_f(a, h)$ used herein are listed in Table 1. Thus, G_c is calculated from the onset load using Equation (3), and the mode mix is computed from the measured angle at that load, ϕ , and Equation (2). However, the onset of matrix cracking occurs prior to the onset of planar delamination growth [6,7]. Therefore, while it is expected that the calculated ERR is reasonably accurate prior to the onset of transverse cracking, it cannot be used to determine a valid toughness subsequent to transverse crack initiation. It is expected, however, that the ERR will still qualitatively reflect a measure of the energy expended in creating a unit of newly delaminated surface area, and it is subsequently used in this sense.

Delamination Length, a (mm)	32	70	127	32	70
Thickness, 2h (mm)	3.0	3.0	3.0	6.0	6.0
$C_f(a, h)$	1.98	3.72	5.70	2.24	4.02

Table 1: Correction factors for ERR determination

3.3 Stress Intensity Factors

Stress intensity factors for SST specimens can be determined from the components of ERR given by Equation (1). The relationships between G_i and K_i ($i=I, II, III$) for orthotropic materials are given by Refs. [28,29] in a traditional coordinate system, where y is the thickness and z the width direction. These equations were transformed to the conventional laminated plate theory coordinate system used in Figures 1, 2 and 4 in Ref. [30], where they were applied to cracks between two dissimilar orthotropic materials. For a single, homogeneous, transversely isotropic material, they reduce to:

$$K_I = \sqrt{\frac{4 G_I}{H_{11}}}, \quad K_{III} = \sqrt{\frac{2 G_{III}}{H_3}} \quad (4)$$

where

$$H_3 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{G_{23} G_{12}}} \quad (5)$$

and for $\sigma_{y'y'} = 0$

$$H_{11} = 2 \left\{ 2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{E_{11}^3 E_{33}}} \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{2 G_{13}} - \frac{v_{13}}{E_{11}} \right) \sqrt{E_{11} E_{33}} \right) \right\}^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

whereas for $\varepsilon_{y'y'} = 0$

$$H_{11} = 2 \left\{ 2 \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{E_{11}} - \frac{v_{13}^2 E_{33}}{E_{11}^2} \right)^3 \left(\frac{1}{E_{33}} - \frac{v_{23}^2}{E_{33}} \right)} \left(1 - \frac{\frac{v_{13}}{E_{11}} + \frac{v_{13} v_{23}}{E_{11}} - \frac{1}{G_{13}}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{E_{11}} - \frac{v_{13}^2 E_{33}}{E_{11}^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{E_{33}} - \frac{v_{23}^2}{E_{33}} \right)}}} \right) \right\}^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

In the above, conventional laminated plate theory notation is used [30]. For isotropic materials, these reduce to the more familiar relationships

$$K_I = \sqrt{E' G_I}, \quad K_{III} = \sqrt{2 \mu G_{III}} \quad (8)$$

where $E' = E$ for $\sigma_{y'y'} = 0$, $E' = E/(1-\nu^2)$ for $\varepsilon_{y'y'} = 0$, and μ is the shear modulus.

3.4 Transverse Crack Angle

In this work, transverse crack orientation will be measured experimentally and correlated to predictions based on the calculated mode I-III conditions at the delamination front. To make these predictions, the minimum strain energy density (SED) criterion [31,32], maximum ERR criterion [33,34], and maximum principal tensile stress (MPTS) criterion [17,18,20,35] were considered. Ref. [32] showed that the minimum SED criterion predicts a crack rotation angle of 0° , that is, no rotation at all, for mode III loading. As such, this criterion is considered insensitive to mode III loading, and is not appropriate for this work. Considering the maximum ERR criterion, Ref. [35] showed that this criterion exhibits a bifurcation at a value of K_{III}/K_I that depends on material properties. Predicted crack angles by the maximum ERR criterion agree with those from the MPTS criterion prior to this bifurcation. Subsequent to it, the maximum ERR predictions are different and contain two branches whose meanings are unclear and whose results are contradicted by experiment. Consequently, in this work the MPTS criterion is adopted.

Formulating the MPTS criterion for orthotropic material properties yields the predicted echelon array crack angle, θ , as

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{K_{III}}{\frac{1}{2} K_I (1 - \gamma)} \right) \quad (9)$$

where $\gamma = 0$ for $\sigma_{y'y'} = 0$, and, for $\varepsilon_{y'y'} = 0$

$$\gamma = \frac{\nu_{12} E_{22}}{E_{11}} + \nu_{23} \quad (10)$$

For isotropic materials, Equation (10) reduces to the more familiar form $\gamma = 2\nu$ [35]. For comparison to experimental results, a predicted echelon crack orientation may be obtained from the measured specimen rotation angle ϕ by substituting Equations (1) and (4) into Equation (9), resulting in

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2H_{11}}{H_3}} \frac{\cot \phi}{(1 - \gamma)} \right) \quad (11)$$

4 RESULTS

4.1 Apparent Toughness Tests

At least three delamination toughness tests were performed on each of the SST geometries of Table 1. The apparent toughness, calculated using Equation (3), is plotted against specimen rotation angle and mode mixity in Figures 5a and b, respectively. Small rotations are associated with larger toughness and larger mode III components. Figure 5b appears to show the apparent toughness approaching an asymptotic value as the rotation angle, and percentage of G_I , decreases. Conversely, larger specimen rotations are associated with larger mode I components and lower apparent toughnesses. We point out that at small G_{III}/G_I , the lowest apparent toughness measured here appears to be below the mode I delamination toughness for IM7/8552 of approximately 200 J/m^2 [36]. However, the near-tip transverse cracks initiate well before the onset of delamination advance in these specimens [6] and, for all geometries, the point of macroscopic advance reflected in the apparent toughness represents the growth of the coupled system of transverse cracks and the planar delamination after the transverse cracks have initiated. This produces inaccuracies in the toughness calculations, and also means that delamination growth is not occurring in the conventional sense of the advance of a single planar delamination. For this reason, the term ‘‘apparent toughness’’ is utilized. As shown in Figure 5, this provides a means to examine the underlying mechanisms contributing to the observed dependencies of apparent toughness on test geometry that have been observed in previous mode III testing.

4.2 Effect of Geometry on Matrix Cracking

Figure 6 presents photomicrographs from three 24-ply SST specimens tested with different insert lengths. These sections are from a plane approximately 2 mm ahead of the Teflon insert in each specimen, where the fracture surfaces are well developed. Each image also shows the value of G_{III}/G_I at which planar delamination advance occurred, calculated from the associated specimen rotation angle using Equation (2). All three sections shown in Figure 6 display the coupled matrix cracking and planar delamination that is expected for unidirectional SST specimens. However, it is clear that the fracture surfaces are evolving differently within the three geometries. For the 24-ply, $a = 32$ mm specimen shown in Figure 6a, G_{III}/G_I is relatively high, and the transverse matrix cracks emanate from the mid-plane in approximately straight lines at angles close to 45° . It is pointed out that the fracture surfaces of 48-ply specimens of both $a = 32$ mm and $a = 70$ mm, where G_{III}/G_I is also typically high, look very similar to the fracture surface presented in Figure 6a.

For the 24-ply, $a = 70$ mm specimen shown in Figure 6b, where G_{III}/G_I is notably lower, the transverse cracking behavior is different. Here, large transverse cracks clearly emanate from the mid-plane, but there are also small branch cracks extending from the mid-plane and intersecting the larger matrix cracks, as noted by the arrows in this figure. Additionally, while the transverse matrix cracks are very straight in Figure 6a, in Figure 6b they are more s-shaped. Because of this, the vertical height of the matrix cracks in the $a = 70$ mm specimens may be limited, as after some amount of growth these cracks are more likely to turn, and in some cases extend a short amount horizontally. Note that there is no apparent propensity for the horizontal extension of the transverse cracks to occur at the interlaminar interfaces.

The transverse section of Figure 6c is from a 24-ply, $a = 127$ mm specimen. Here, matrix cracks initiate at very shallow angles, and almost immediately turn to approximately horizontal orientations. This is consistent with the relatively large mode I component in these specimens, and is a more dramatic manifestation of the behaviors observed in the specimen of Figure 6b. The arrows in Figure 6c point to instances where the transverse cracks curve and turn back to re-link with the mid-plane. As a result, the transverse cracks in these specimens rarely extend past the first ply bounding the delamination on either side, and it is difficult to differentiate the planar delamination from the transverse cracks.

Figure 5: Plots of apparent G_c versus (a) specimen rotation at delamination tip, (b) mode mixity.

4.3 Matrix Crack Orientation

Figure 7 presents photomicrographs from the same specimens as Figure 6, but these were obtained from section cuts that were within 0.5 mm of the end of the original Teflon inserts. The transverse matrix cracks in Figure 7 are much smaller than those in the corresponding images of Figure 6, and the matrix crack turning observed in Figures 6b-c has not yet developed. Whereas the images of Figure 6 depict well-developed fracture surfaces, those of Figure 7 represent the way that they initially form. That is, the cracks shown in Figure 6 developed to their particular size and shape under the influence of an already cracked matrix, whereas those in Figure 7 formed adjacent to the original, undamaged configuration associated with the preimplanted Teflon insert. It follows that predictions of transverse crack orientations using Equation (11) would be expected to correlate more closely to what is

displayed in the images shown in Figure 7. Note, however, that these images represent only a small portion of each specimen's width. Therefore, in order to accurately obtain and compare the matrix crack orientations within the different geometries to each other and to predicted results, graphical analyses were used to measure the orientations of every crack across the specimens' width.

In order to predict the transverse crack orientation, θ , by the MPTS criterion (Equation 11), one requires the experimentally measured rotation of the delamination front, ϕ , the full set of material properties for a transversely isotropic material, and an assumption about whether the transverse strain, $\varepsilon_{y'y'}$, or stress, $\sigma_{y'y'}$, equals zero. Table 2 presents properties utilized by Ref. [37] for IM7/8552. As the values of E_{11} and G_{12} in this table are different than those determined experimentally as part of this study, and as it is likely that $\varepsilon_{y'y'} = 0$ is more appropriate for the center of the specimen whereas $\sigma_{y'y'} = 0$ is more appropriate near its edges, a sensitivity study was conducted to assess how the predicted value of θ would be affected. To this end, the various values of material properties were considered, including isotropic material properties with $\nu = 0.32$, under conditions of both $\varepsilon_{y'y'} = 0$ and $\sigma_{y'y'} = 0$. For the range of ϕ measured in this work ($3-30^\circ$), it was found that the predicted matrix crack orientation, θ , varied by 3.5% or less for these variations. As a result of this insensitivity, the values from Table 2 and the assumption that $\varepsilon_{y'y'} = 0$ are used in what follows.

Figure 8 presents normalized transverse matrix crack angle measurements versus mode mixity. It can be seen that Equation (11) over-predicts the transverse matrix crack angle, and that the accuracy of the predictions improves with increasing G_{III}/G_I . The accuracy of the predicted values of θ in Figure 8, and the trend of the comparisons of theory to experiment as a function of mode mixity, are quite similar to what has been reported for homogenous materials [35,38]. In this sense, the results in the figure provide corroborating evidence for the presence of the mode I field.

Figure 6: Representative transverse section images of 24-ply specimens with different delamination lengths (a) 32 mm, (b) 70 mm, (c) 127 mm, taken approximately 2 mm ahead of the Teflon insert.

Figure 7: Representative transverse section images of 24-ply specimens just ahead of the Teflon insert for different delamination lengths (a) 32 mm, (b) 70 mm, (c) 127 mm.

$E_{11} = 161.0 \text{ GPa}$	$E_{22} = 11.38 \text{ GPa}$	$E_{33} = 11.38 \text{ GPa}$
$\nu_{12} = 0.32$	$\nu_{13} = 0.32$	$\nu_{23} = 0.436$
$G_{12} = 5.17 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{13} = 5.17 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{23} = 3.98 \text{ GPa}$

Table 2: IM7/8552 Material Properties [37].

4.4 Effect of Geometry on Fracture Surface Evolution

The manner in which the fracture surfaces evolve with increasing delamination growth was examined using the method described in Ref. [21]. Multiple transverse sections cuts, at increasing distances from the Teflon insert, were made in 24-ply SST specimens which had 12 – 14 mm of

delamination growth. All visible cracks in each image were counted and measured, and the average matrix crack size and number of matrix cracks was evaluated as a function of the distance from the Teflon insert. Results were consistent with the coarsening behaviors reported in Ref. [21]: matrix crack length increased to a limiting value, and the number of matrix cracks decreased to a limiting value, with increasing distance from the Teflon insert. The number of cracks at a given distance ahead of the insert was similar in all specimens. Although the trends were similar, the maximum transverse crack length (i.e., the limiting value) varied among specimens: the larger the mode I component, the smaller the maximum crack length. This is attributable to the increasingly curved crack path with increasing mode I evidenced in Figure 6.

In addition to the above, the data at each cross sectional location, for each specimen, was combined to arrive at an “average” or “typical” transverse crack for that specimen and section. As shown in Figure 9, these average results were then used to illustrate the evolution of transverse cracking for the three different specimens. In this figure, the value at which any transverse crack intersects the horizontal axis represents the distance from the Teflon insert to the section cut represented by that crack. These distances correspond to those given in the figure legends. Otherwise, the mm scales on the vertical and horizontal axes present the profile of an “average crack” from each section as viewed with the DIC microscope. The left-most data set therefore represents a typical transverse crack that forms quite close to the Teflon insert, and the data sets to the right of it show how the crack evolves, i.e., they depict the appearance of typical cracks at subsequent cross sections.

Figure 9a shows transverse crack profiles from the $a = 32$ mm specimen. It can be seen here that there was a significant increase in crack length over the first few millimeters of growth, after which the crack length only increased slightly. The minor increases in crack length seen in the profiles further ahead of the Teflon insert are accompanied by the development of a slight s-shape, although in general the orientation of the crack does not change very much as it grows. Similar behaviors are seen in the profiles of a crack from an $a = 70$ mm specimen shown in Figure 9b. There is a large increase in crack length in the first few millimeters of growth, after which the crack length stabilizes. The s-shape is more pronounced in this specimen, although the orientation of the crack near the mid-plane remains relatively constant. The s-shape crack profiles likely develop due to the combination of the fiber constraints on crack path and the changing mode mixity during delamination growth. It is known that the matrix cracks lead the growth of the planar delamination [6]. However, as the planar delamination grows, the amount of specimen twist at the delamination front increases, which increases the mode I component. As predicted by Equation (11), this should result in increasingly shallow matrix cracks, as is observed experimentally for homogenous materials where crack segments twist as they extend [17,35]. However, in the composite laminates studied herein, the presence of the carbon fibers prevents the matrix cracks from significantly rotating once they have formed. However, as the matrix cracks are also increasing in length as they extend through the specimen, the *additional* crack growth is locally oriented towards that predicted by the MPTS criterion, resulting in the s-shape that is frequently seen.

The crack profile from the $a = 127$ mm specimen in Figure 9c represents an extension of the above phenomena. The very first increment of matrix crack growth is straight (in agreement with Figure 7c). However, very soon thereafter, the crack develops an s-shaped profile due to the large amount of rotation and the associated mode I component. The relinking of these cracks with the mid-plane is similar to the factory roof profile produced by the linking of type A and B zones in homogeneous materials, and energetically follows a similar argument [17].

4.5 Comparison of Composite Fracture Surface Evolution to Homogenous Materials

Fracture surface evolution in composite and homogenous materials subjected to predominantly mode III loadings starts off identically, via the emergence of an echelon array of transverse cracks along the front of the initial, planar crack or delamination. This produces crack front segmentation and faceting. In homogeneous materials, the transverse cracks twist as they extend and, if growth of the initially planar crack occurs, it is accompanied by twisting in-between facets [12,13]. Both types of twisting represent the tendency of cracks in homogenous materials to grow under mode I conditions. In laminated composites, however, both types of twisting are constrained. Once a matrix crack is

created it is not able to substantially change its orientation due to its bounding fibers. Thus, rather than the twisting that occurs in homogenous materials, in composite laminates the transverse cracks will become s-shaped under mixed-mode I-III loadings. Further, the amount by which transverse cracks can extend in a composite laminate is limited by the close proximity of the laminate’s free surfaces. This is not generally an issue in homogeneous specimens. The fibers also constrain the delamination from twisting, and this fact, combined with the presence of an interlaminar interface and the limited ability of the transverse cracks to absorb energy due to limitations on their length, results in a coupled, concurrent planar advance in composites that is not observed in homogenous materials. Thus, the constraints that the fibers place on both transverse crack and planar delamination twisting, the proximity of the free surfaces, and the presence of an interlaminar interface combine to produce a very different fracture surface evolution in the unidirectional SST specimens studied herein in comparison to that which has been observed in homogeneous materials.

Figure 8: Ratio of experimentally measured transverse crack angles ($\theta_{\text{Experimental}}$) to predictions from the maximum principal tensile stress criterion ($\theta_{\text{Theoretical}}$) versus mode mixity.

Figure 9: Evolution of representative cracks from transverse sections of specimens with delamination lengths of (a) 32 mm, (b) 70 mm, (c) 127 mm.

5 APPLICATION TO MODE III DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS TESTING

The results presented herein and in previous, related studies [5-7,21] indicate two fundamental problems with mode III toughness tests of composite tape laminates. First, for any geometry, small transverse cracks initiate prior to delamination advance. For specimens where the adjacent plies have their fibers oriented in the direction of growth, such as in geometries used for mode I and mode II testing, the growth of these transverse cracks is unconstrained. This indicates that alternative layups will be required for tests that include mode III. As discussed in Refs. [7,21], it is possible that alternative layups can bound the length of the transverse cracks to be analogous to the micro-cracking that occurs prior to delamination in unidirectional mode II specimens.

The second problem with testing relates specifically to split beam geometries, where the mode mixity at the onset of delamination advance depends on specimen twist and therefore on specimen and test geometry. To obtain mode III conditions, it would be necessary to restrain the twisting during testing, for example in the shear-torsion-bending test [29] which uses rollers, or the improved split cantilever beam test [39] which used thick steel blocks bonded to the specimen. In view of the first issue above, however, one would also need to change to non-unidirectional geometries. This would create considerable problems in the development of an accurate data reduction methodology. Thus,

pursuing a variation of the edge-crack torsion test, as proposed in Refs. [7,21], is perhaps the most promising approach.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The influence of specimen twisting during anti-plane shear (mode III) loading was studied using the split-shear torsion test. It was shown that specimen twisting causes a mode I stress intensity factor to develop that is proportional to the angle of twist, thereby producing mixed-mode I-III conditions along the delamination front. The orientations of the near-tip transverse matrix cracks that develop were shown to agree fairly well with predictions based on a maximum principal tensile stress criterion. This was shown to influence the apparent toughness, in that a larger angle of twist at fracture corresponded to larger mode I conditions and a smaller value of apparent G_c . This effect, combined with the fact that the transverse cracks initiate prior to delamination advance, appear to explain the observed dependency of the apparent toughness on test geometry in split-shear torsion specimens. The amount of twist was also shown to affect the way that the fracture surfaces evolve, and explanations were provided why this evolution differs from that observed in homogeneous materials. These findings were used to make some observations and recommendations regarding future delamination toughness testing. They also have strong implications for predictions of the onset and growth of delaminations in practical structural geometries, in that the amount of mode III that is present can produce behaviors that heretofore have not commonly been recognized to occur.

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